

COVERING OF THE ISSUES OF THE YOUNG POPULATION IN THE TRANS-CAUCASIAN REGION BY THE PRINTED MEDIA ON THE GEORGIAN INSTANCE**Mariam Marghia***Ph. D. Student of Mass Communication Doctoral Educational Program
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Chargali Str. 73, 0141, Tbilisi, Georgia***Abstract**

Printed media in Georgia of the 21st century is not in a favorable state. A practice of dissemination of magazines and newspapers in the printed form has been decreasing step-by-step. From this viewpoint the largest impact had been inflicted by the coronavirus challenge. In the pandemic period the paused and suspended life style had a negative effect on the Georgian press. Financial crisis forced many magazines and newspapers to operate in the online mode or to interrupt their functionality completely.

Internet development provides receiving and processing of information in a simple and rapid mode. A large part of the society, especially young people, may get information from any point of the world quicker and more comfortably using the so called “gadgets”. The stated popularizes an opinion that this part of the audience ignores traditional media. Preservation of the young audience having contemporary attitudes and many opportunities oriented on the constant development is very important for media. Thus, media should actively talk about the problems existing in a definite region and challenges existing in front of the young people. Intensive attention of local media outlets regarding problematic issues is the most profitable way for their resolving and relevant informing of the community.

A target of the stated research is to represent a significance of covering of the issues being actual for the Georgian youth, as well as the problems and challenges they usually face, to distinguish a role of the regional media in the part of covering of the topics popular among young people.

Keywords: young population (the youth), Transcaucasian region, Georgia, regional, newspaper, covering, “Guria News”.

Introduction

Tens of TV-channels, radio stations, magazines, newspapers and news agencies work in Georgia. Despite of this fact, a key source for receiving of information by the society is TV and online platform. With the account of results of the research of the Georgian audience held by the “Thomson Reuters Foundation”, 84% of interviewees use television, and only 15% - press (newspapers) to receive information. (Mdznarishvili n.d.).

The most popular are central, capital-based media outlets. However, in Georgia, regional media is also broadcasting in all forms. It is noteworthy that local media has to struggle against diversified challenges. For instance, deficiency of budget, cadres, materials, low rating, necessity of renovation of technical and material base and others. Regional editions appeared in front of different critical challenges within the state after the corona virus pandemics. Many of them were forced to proceed their functionality in online mode or to interrupt it fully. Editions, which had overcome this period and circumstances try to suggest an interesting content to their readers and to take diversity of the auditory into account.

Against the background of developing of internet in the last years a popular idea appeared and it suggested that the oldest representative of traditional media, - printed media will be gradually adjusted to the online space. Attitude of the young population regard-

ing the simplified methods of getting information is actual for strengthening of this idea. Preserving of the young auditoria’s interests and attention is of a key importance for the traditional media, and for frequent discussing of the issues being interesting and actual for them.

The stated research is targeted at distinguishing of a significance of the regional press on the instance of the newspaper “Guria News”, representing of its role in the part of covering of the youth’s issues. In frames of the research, we processed 262 editions of the printed media outlets of “Guria News” issued in 2020-2024 which are recently kept in the National Library of the Parliament of Georgia.

A method of content analysis is used as a key method of research for the article. By using of this method we can clearly review a direction, a style, priorities of the subjects of research, a contentive load of materials and others.

Discussion and results

In direction of reporting of the young population’s issues the Georgian regional press does not express a particular attention. Local editions majorly cover political processes and different activities of the local government. Besides, they often write about social-economic problems existing in the region. However, there are editions which try to satisfy interests of the readers of different tastes, for instance “Guria News”.

“Guria News” is an 8 paged weekly newspaper. It operates on the online-platform gurianews.com. We

can say that the newspaper is diversified. It describes problems being actual for the regions, and attracts attention in relation to the general news occurring in the state. It has different rubrics with the contents creating representation about the focus of the media outlet. The newspaper has an historic rubric which describes different people and events happening in different periods of time and narrates about different historical periods not only of Georgia, but of the whole world as well.

The rubric “Farmstead”. Materials used in it describe different directions of the agricultural sector: land-cultivation, fruit planting, citrus planting and others.

The edition constantly writes about different problems existing in the region, particularly it reports about infrastructural and transport-related problems, deficiency of water, absence of natural gas and others. In 2020 almost all editions were covering an issue about spreading of street dogs and complaints in the population. It indicated to the necessity of having a dog shelter and high actuality of the problem.

The edition was actively involved in the social campaign being important during the pandemics. The message “Make a vaccine” was constantly printed on the first page of the newspaper. Besides, it wrote about a necessity of distance protection. The edition was covering a significance of following of rules of home cleaning, hygiene norms and disinfection during the pandemics. It recommended to readers materials on the following topics: “How to clean the house during the coronavirus pandemics?” (Guria News #22, 2020), “How to help children in the period of self-isolation and quarantines – the pediatrician’s advices?” (“Guria News” #22, 2020).

Media outlet actively covers decisions adopted by the local government, different infrastructural and social programs, local problems. We can say that the edition tries to fulfill a local “regulatory” function of the regional media.

For the stated research “Guria News” became interesting due to its specific supplement – “Below 21”. It has the following inscription: “Young newspaper of Guria” and it often contains 3-4 pages. It is an integral part of the newspaper and authors of the materials are represented by journalists of “Guria News”. Majorly it is devoted to interesting young people, changes and news implemented in the educational system and successful students. The focus is seen in the headlines of the materials: “In Ozurgeti the Etalon’s student was revealed” (Tavberidze, 2020), “Which rules must be followed by the school graduates on the exam?” (Guria News, 2020), “What the student should know about the obtained state academic grant – bans and rights?” (Guria News, N15 2024), “State scholarship is being doubled for successful students” (#36, Guria News, 2023) and others.

The newspaper often covers sport news. It reports about current events occurring in the field of the world sport; on top of all a great attention is paid on popularizing of successful sportsmen residing in the region of Guria and teams among the society, covering of histories of their victory. In 2020 the newspaper published

materials about the girls’ football team based in Lanchkhuti with the following title: “A successful debut of football player girls from Lanchkhuti in the Champion’s League” (S. Tsilosani, 2020) and “Lanchkhutian girls drove crazy the whole world” (Tsilosani, 2020).

The newspaper’s pages review not only sports teams, but separate successful sportsmen and their individual histories. The media outlet in 2020 wrote about Khvicha Kvaratskhelia: “A 19 years old boy kicks the ball in the Georgian manner and his fans are proud of him”. It was the period when Kvaratskhelia played in the team “Rubin” and hadn’t been recognized as a well-known football star. The materials talk about Khvicha’s intelligence and particular opportunities. The article is owed to the portal sportall.ge and the edition has made a relevant indication. (Guria News, #40 2020) The media outlet pays a great attention to histories of success of local sportsmen. Materials are small-sized, majorly carrying descriptive and informative character, however the titles reflect the newspaper’s focus where local origination of sportsmen is underscored. For instance: “A resident of Lanchkhuti Otar Janelidze is a champion of Georgia” (S. Tsilosani, 2020), “Which Gurian sportsmen will take a part in the European Championship?” (Girkelidze, 2020) and others.

The edition often suggests to readers portraits of interesting young people who are distinctive due to their profession, history of success, ingenuity of the field of activities, education or other characteristic details. Readers got from “Guria News” information about a 21 years old Ozurgetian boy who teaches computer programs to the senior generation. According to the materials, the respondent works in frames of one of the projects and shares his knowledge and experience to the citizens over 60 years (Girkelidze, “A 21 years old Ozurgetian boy who teaches computer programs to the senior generation”, 2020).

The newspaper often covers successful academic performance and achievements of local young people. The materials prepared about them contain a large number of the articles of such content. It is noteworthy that majorly general information is given in the information materials of small size which briefly describe a success of a definite person and is ended with the name of scholarship, educational grants and other similar issue. Such materials are not rare on the pages of the “Guria News”.

“Guria News” pays attention on other more significant issues. It recommends to read authorized blogs as well as blogs taken from different on online-portal. For instance: “Books which must be read” (Guria News #53, 2020); the article includes prominent works of the world literature such as Erich Maria Remarque’s “Borrowed life”, the George Orwell “1984”, Gabriel Garcia Marquez “One hundred years of loneliness” and others. The author for attracting of the reader’s interest suggests a brief resume on each work. The edition suggested an article of the similar content via educational applications and web-sites. (Guria News, #50 2020), (#11, #17 web-site which make you cleverer” 2021). The next material of entertaining and recreational content is about films. The media outlet suggests to the

reader 7 films from the field of travelling. The films are selected from the filmography of well-known and successful directors such as Woody Allen, Shon Pen, Ben Stiller and others (#11, "TOP-7 the most interesting adventurous films", 2020).

The edition focuses its attention on the problems which are spread in a routine life of the youth. One of the materials reviews results of the research conducted by the "Agency of the Youth", regarding the challenges faced by the youth, their employment and the problems connected with it, programs and services designed for young population in the municipality, opportunity for entertaining and relaxing, using of health protection services. The material in a rather interesting way represents results of the research and suggests a kind of a resume to readers. It underscores significant issues which is a definite representation of the problems actual for the young people (Girkelidze, "Which problems are actual for the young people residing in Ozurgeti and what are their demands?", 2021).

Another one interesting article for the young population describes the difficulties existing while selecting one's profession. The material reflects opinions of several young people who draw attention on different problems. The article's author refers to results of the IPM's research to confirm that a comparatively larger part of the Georgian young population -36,8% selects a profession of social scientists and journalists. Respondents of the article personally state that in the process of planning of the career involving of the school, and family is essential; profession-oriented seminars have not been formed for the young people yet. It is supplemented with meetings of different professionals with the young people to demonstrate difficulties and privileges of a definite profession clearly. We can say that the article is prepared on a rather high qualified level. It reflects opinions of main heroes of a definite news, young people, as well as of psychologists, experts of the educational field. Finally, the article separated different problems realizing and considering of which is a precondition for their settlement (Pachulia, 2021).

Migration of people from village to city, for the last years, became particularly vivid. Migration of not only emigrants, but of the population and particularly young people in different towns of the country is conditioned by different problems, including a large number of working places in the city in comparison with village, more favorable conditions of life, opportunities for receiving of a higher education and others. The article devoted to the stated issue is prepared by "Guria News". On the question "Why young people leave village?" the edition gives the following answer: "They reason is an improper operation of social transport, deficiency of water, infrastructural problems". The author underscores a significance of young people for development of the village as well as in direction of its strengthening. A main mechanism of settlement of problems, according to the author, is explained by a specific significance of involving of the government, a necessity of existence of different targeted programs, supporting of an entrepreneurial activity and a necessity of rising motivation among the youth in this way. (Oniani, 2020).

Conclusion

If we summarize the stated regarding the edition "Guria News" we may say that the edition tries to adjust to readers with any preferences, to be a diversified and interesting, to suggest to the auditory local and nationwide interesting news. It is remarkable that the media outlet is generally focused on the region of Guria. As for the youth-oriented direction of the newspaper it, on top of separate materials, has a 2-4 paged youth's newspaper "Below 21" which is a supplement to the "Guria News". In 2020 the supplement "Below 21" represented diversified, interesting, significant, youth-related news and information. It acquainted the auditory with portraits of successful young people and educational news. Naturally, from the viewpoint of the media outlet working over the youth-related magazine represented as a supplement is very pleasant, but after the year of 2020 the "Below 21" became a rather apparent. Since the year of 2021 it majorly covers changes entered into the educational space, news of the Ministry of Education and National Examination Center that deprives a niche and forms it as an edition disseminating a similar information.

In frames of the represented article all counterparts of the "Guria News" for 2020-2024 kept in the National Library of the Parliament of Georgia (totally 262 editions) had been processed. It is noteworthy that in this number of counterparts we recognized as interesting for the research only 116 materials. Despite of the fact that almost all numbers were represented in the form of the supplement "Below 21", after the year of 2020, the youth-focused newspaper usually covered news existing in the educational field and the information existing around the national examinations. The edition is rarely interested in other significant issues being actual for young people, such as teenager's age and news connected with it, bulling, a rule of healthy life, problems of employment and others.

With the account of results of the research, we can say that the "Guria News" definitely considers a specific weight of young people in the auditory and tries to draw main attention to the issues interesting for them. The edition is devoted to "light" entertaining, cognitive and relatively complicated issues. During the period being under research the edition makes a representation of the young people residing in the region. Readers are informed about the problems, challenges and positive changes existing in front of the local young people. From the side of media outlets paying of attention on similar topics may be recognized as a step forward on the way of settlement of definite problematic issues.

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